

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

D.1.3.2 Data-gaps and data improvement report

Final version

05 2025

Partner responsible: CSI Piemonte

Main Author: Tatsiana Hubina, Claudio Bedin

Delivery Date: 30.05.2025

DISCLAIMER

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

DOCUMENT SHEET

Project Acronym	Climate_CRICES
Full title	Increasing Climate Change Resilience in Central Europe
Grant Agreement number	CE0200728
Coordinator	Veneto Region
Website	https://www.interreg-central.eu/projects/climate_crices/

Deliverable number	D.1.3.2
Deliverable name	Data-gaps and data improvement report
Lead Beneficiary	CSI Piemonte
WP	WP1
Activity title	A1.3 Analysis of the (open) data contribution for the development of climate change management plans
Type	REPORT
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Delivery date	31/05/2025
Main Author	CSI Piemonte and All Partners
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15606969

Executive Summary

This document addresses the issue of data gaps relevant to the Climate_CRICES project and their implications for climate adaptation planning across Central Europe.

Initially, during the project application phase, its purpose was limited to identifying available data sources for integration into the platform and highlighting missing ones. However, as implementation progressed, the scope evolved to include a more in-depth assessment of stakeholder and project needs. It includes a structured analysis of indicator selection and data availability.

The report outlines the methodology used to identify climate-related indicators that serve as the foundation for monitoring climate impacts. It also maps out the corresponding data sources required to populate these indicators and summarizes the progress made by project partners in overcoming data limitations.

In total, 223 regional datasets and 64 European/global data sources were selected by May 2025. These were assessed for their relevance, accessibility, and alignment with project needs. The document also includes insights from stakeholder workshops and describes the common metadata structure that underpins the dashboard.

A major added value of this work is the opportunity to compare climate adaptation plans—and the processes behind their development—across Central European regions. This comparative perspective supports mutual learning, the identification of good practices, and a clearer view of shared challenges.

Finally, the report presents a set of solutions to address persistent data gaps, including use of global data sources, metadata harmonization, structured comparison of adaptation strategies, and a user-friendly dashboard for transparent visualization and cross-regional policy alignment.

Table of Contents

<u>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY</u>	2
<u>1 INTRODUCTION</u>	4
<u>2 METHODOLOGY FOR ANALYSING EXISTING DATA STRUCTURES AND ESTABLISHING A COMMON PARTNERSHIP FRAMEWORK</u>	8
2.1 THE PROCESS USED TO SELECT CLIMATE-RELATED INDICATORS	8
2.2 IMPACTS AND INDICATORS LISTS	8
2.3 COMMON PARTNERSHIP FRAMEWORK, ENTITIES ANALYSIS	9
2.4 STRUCTURED DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	9
2.5 ENTITY-RELATIONSHIP MAPPING.....	11
2.6 DASHBOARD TO SUPPORT DECISION - MAKING.....	13
<u>3 OUTCOMES OF PARTNER’S ANALYSES</u>	16
3.1 LIST OF MISSING INDICATORS (FROM STRATEGIES AND PLANS)	16
3.2 LIST OF ADDITIONAL IMPORTANT INDICATORS (FROM STRATEGIES AND PLANS)	17
3.3 INPUTS FROM THE FIRST LOCAL WORKSHOPS (MISSING AND ADDITIONAL INDICATORS)	17
<u>4 DATA-GAPS AND SOLUTIONS</u>	19
4.1 BASED ON THE DATASET ANALYSIS	19
4.2 BASED ON THE CROSS-BORDER COOPERATION ANALYSIS	23
<u>5 LESSONS LEARNED</u>	25
<u>6 CONCLUSIONS</u>	26
<u>7 ANNEXES</u>	27
7.1 TABLE SUMMARIZING THE IMPACTS (CLIMATE CHANGE RISKS).....	27
7.2 TABLE SUMMARIZING THE INDICATORS	30
7.3 WORKFLOW TIMELINE FOR DATA STRUCTURING AND INTEGRATION	37

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents a comprehensive assessment of data availability and gaps relevant to the Climate_CRICES project, focusing on climate adaptation planning across Central Europe. Initially conceived as a simple inventory of missing data, the scope of this report has evolved into a structured analysis of both stakeholder needs and project-level data challenges. It builds on the foundations laid in Deliverable D.1.3.1, expanding the understanding of how metadata, indicators, and climate change adaptation plan-level inputs can be structured for cross-border comparison and dashboard integration.

Why This Framework Was Needed

Many existing climate information systems—reviewed in Deliverable D.1.3.1—excel in providing detailed geospatial data, but fall short when it comes to offering clear, accessible insights into policy relevance or strategic planning. Moreover, they often lack multilingual access, are targeted at technical users, and do not allow easy comparison of climate change adaptation plans across territories. The Climate_CRICES project seeks to address these gaps by organizing both data and strategic information around a shared structure that facilitates transparency, comparability, and stakeholder engagement.

To operationalize this, partner CSI (PP03) developed a structured data collection methodology in collaboration with the full partnership. Key elements of this approach include:

- ✓ A set of common entities: impacts, risks, indicators, objectives, and adaptation measures.
- ✓ Definitions of relationships between these entities.
- ✓ Harmonized classification systems and metadata templates.
- ✓ A common glossary to ensure linguistic and conceptual alignment across countries.

This methodology enables partners to extract structured data from largely unstructured climate strategies and feed it into a relational data model. These entities were the foundation for building a relational understanding of how adaptation is structured and implemented across regions. Figure 1 below illustrates the Climate_CRICES data collection methodology.

Figure 1- Climate_CRICES Data Collection Methodology

The initial methodological step was to associate available datasets with specific indicators, thereby linking raw data with the key climate-related elements outlined in strategic plans. This structured data collection was essential, as traditional adaptation plans are typically presented as unstructured text, making systematic comparison and data integration extremely difficult.

Figure 2 - Climate_CRICES harmonized Methodology Workflow

Figure 3- Climate_CRICES Common Methodology for Data Classification and Harmonization, Roadmap

2 Methodology for Analysing Existing Data Structures and Establishing a Common Partnership Framework

2.1 The process used to select climate-related indicators

The process of selecting the relevant impacts and the indicators linked to them was carried out in working groups. To harmonise the outputs, activities in all three project focus areas (heat and drought, flooding and biodiversity) were conducted in a coordinated manner, with the cooperation of the working group leaders PP09 (UJEP, Heat & Drought), PP08 (UPWr, Flooding), PP04 (FB, Biodiversity), and the work package leader PP07 (IOER). The compiled list of impacts and indicators was then subjected to feedback from all project partners. The most frequent comments raised concerns about the availability of data or the relevance of certain indicators to specific areas. Only a few indicators were added or adjusted based on this feedback.

The identification and selection of the core set of impacts and indicators were based on an extensive analysis of key documents addressing climate change impacts, as well as a specific review of the scientific literature. The reports (within [Sixth Assessment Report](#)) and other supporting documents of the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) were the basis for identifying key impacts. Other sources were the [EU Adaptation Strategy](#) for impacts and the set of indicators designed and published by the [European Environment Agency for indicators](#).

In this way, a total of 24 impacts and 44 indicators were initially identified. These were further revised in stages, including an assessment of their relevance in the pilot areas and to adaptation policy documents. At this stage, each indicator was accompanied by a description to evaluate its relevance. The method of calculation, the unit of measurement, and the approach to its interpretation. An integral part of this was an assessment of the level at which it is meaningful to monitor the indicator (local/city, regional and national). The next step was to further classify the indicators and to link them to the corresponding impacts/risks categories.

2.2 Impacts and Indicators Lists

This project utilizes a comprehensive set of climate and environmental indicators to assess the impacts of climate change across multiple dimensions. Based on the implementation of the process described above, the current lists include 25 impacts/risks and 44 resp. 45 indicators.

The project identifies a wide range of initial climate change impacts affecting both human and natural systems. These impacts were assessed based on an initial analysis structured into three thematic groups: (i) heat and drought, (ii) flooding, and (iii) impact on biodiversity.

Within these areas, the identified risks include threats to human health and well-being—such as increased heat stress, exposure to urban droughts, and water-related health hazards—as well as significant challenges for agricultural production due to drought, extreme precipitation, and temperature extremes.

Biodiversity is under increasing pressure, with observed impacts such as species loss, altered phenology, habitat degradation, and increased wildfire risk. Flood-related impacts include

damage and mortality risks linked to coastal, river, and inland flooding, often exacerbated by the loss of natural protective ecosystems.

Additional impacts include cascading risks such as water scarcity affecting multiple sectors, physical changes in freshwater systems, soil erosion, hail risk, and loss of snow cover. Changes in land use and the climatic suitability for vegetation and species further emphasize the far-reaching consequences of climate change across Europe.

The indicators cover a wide range of phenomena, including extreme weather events (e.g., hot days, heavy precipitation, droughts, and floods), long-term climatic trends (e.g., temperature and precipitation changes, growing and heating degree days), and ecosystem responses (e.g., changes in biodiversity, vegetation productivity, and species distributions).

In addition, the project integrates indicators related to land use, landscape structure, and socio-economic consequences (e.g., losses in agriculture and infrastructure, number of flood victims). Together, these indicators provide a robust basis for evaluating climate-related risks, ecological vulnerabilities, and adaptation needs across Central Europe (7.1 Table summarizing the impacts (climate change risks)).

The indicators were divided into two basic groups: (i) the indicators that express the so-called meteorological impact and (ii) receptors.

2.3 Common Partnership Framework, Entities Analysis

A key added value of the Climate_CRICES project is its ability to compare climate adaptation plans and implementation experiences across Central European partner countries. This comparative dimension not only fosters mutual learning but also helps identify good practices and common challenges that can inform more effective climate action.

Recognizing the need for structured and comparable inputs, the project team agreed on a common analytical framework to map impacts, risks, indicators, objectives, and measures across partner climate adaptation plans. This shared framework underpins the architecture of the Climate_CRICES dashboard that is not only metadata-rich, but also strategically aligned with regional realities.

2.4 Structured Data Collection and Analysis

Using a collaboratively designed Excel template, partners analysed their respective climate change adaptation plans. This enabled:

- ✓ Uniform metadata generation across partner plans
- ✓ Clear mapping of how strategies address different impacts and indicators
- ✓ Visualization of gaps in policy coverage and data availability

This structured data was used to build the first version of the dashboard (Figures 5 and 6), allowing both technical teams and policymakers to explore how adaptation planning varies across Central

Europe.

Figure 5 - First version of the Climate_CRICES Dashboard Prototype, interface example

Figure 6 - First version of the Climate_CRICES Dashboard Prototype, example of Data representation for indicator monitoring

2.5 Entity-Relationship Mapping

Figures 7 through 9 visually represent the relational model underpinning the dashboard:

- **Figure 7** shows the overall Entity Relationship Diagram, providing a high-level overview of the interconnected data structure.
- **Figure 8** illustrates how common Impact Risks relate to strategic policies, highlighting overlaps and coverage gaps.
- **Figure 9** details the indicator structure, showing links between indicators and impacts, mandatory versus optional classifications, and their presence in partner strategies.

The Entity-Relationship Diagram below provides a high-level overview of the entities and the relationships among them:

Figure 7 - Climate_CRICES Entity and Relationship Diagram

Common list of
ImpactRisk

Common
Classification

Policy Coverage

Impact Risk ID	1. Level 1 Classification	1. Level 2 Classification	2. Level 1 Classification	2. Level 2 Classification	Concrete climate change impacts/risks	Impact description	consistency with the selected adaptation policy		
							Is the impact relevant for your pilot area? (Y/N)	Is the impact covered in your adaptation policy? (Y/N)	Do you have any adaptation/mitigation measures defined in your adaptation policy for this impact? (Y/N)
R1	Heat & Drought	Heatwave			Risk to population	Increased heat stress, mortality and morbidity events from urbanisation	y	y	y
R2	Heat & Drought	Heatwave, General warming			Impacts of climate change on heating and	Climate change, particularly the increase in extreme temperatures,	y	y	y
R3	Biodiversity	Marine ecosystems, Freshwater			Risk of loss of bio	Increases in temperature or changes in precipitation that go beyond the	y	y	y
R4	Heat & Drought	Wildfire	Biodiversity	Terrestrial ecosystems	Increased risk of w	Wildfire that substantially exceeds natural levels can cause extensive tree	y	y	y
R5	Biodiversity	Marine ecosystems			Risk to marine coastal ecosystem	Loss of ecosystem services (income, food, shoreline protection) from rapid	y	y	y
R6	Heat & Drought	Water scarcity			Population at risk	Water shortages in urban areas, and restricted access to water resources	y	y	y
R7	Heat & Drought	Water scarcity	Flooding	Heavy precipitation events	Health risks from water pollution exposure and	Increased environmental health risks when using polluted groundwater.	y	y	y

Figure 8 - ImpactRisk part includes common list of Impact Risks, Common Classification and connection with the Policy (Policy Coverage)

Common list of
ImpactRisk

Common
Classification

Priority Indicators

Policy Coverage

Impact Indicator ID	Indicator name	Classification Level 1	1. Classification Level 2	2. Classification Level 2	3. Classification Level 2	Obligation to be included in the dashboard	consistency with the selected adaptation policy		
							Is indicator relevant for your pilot area? (Y/N)	Is indicator defined in your adaptation policy? (Y/N)	Do you have data for the indicator? (Y/N)
I1	Hot days	Meteorological Impact	Heat & Drought			Mandatory	y	y	y
I2	Heatwave days	Meteorological Impact	Heat & Drought			Mandatory	y	y	y
I3	Tropical nights	Meteorological Impact	Heat & Drought			Optional	y	n	n
I4	Maximum consecutive five-day precipitation	Meteorological Impact	Flooding			Mandatory	y	n	n
I5	Mean temperature	Meteorological Impact	Heat & Drought			Mandatory	n	n	n
I6	Maximum Daily Air Temperature	Meteorological Impact	Heat & Drought			Mandatory	y	y	y
I7	Growing degree days	Receptor	Agriculture	Forestry	Biodiversity	Mandatory	y	y	y

Figure 9 - List of Indicators and relation with Impacts, Common Classification, Key indicators (mandatory or optional) and connection with the Policy (Policy Coverage)

This harmonized, structured approach offers multiple benefits:

- ✓ **Comparability:** Partners can benchmark their strategies against others.
- ✓ **Gap analysis:** Policymakers can quickly identify missing objectives or measures.
- ✓ **Transparency:** The dashboard reveals the underlying data and assumptions used in planning.

Most importantly, this framework supports a common understanding of climate risks and adaptation needs across borders. It transforms fragmented strategic texts into an integrated, policy-relevant dataset.

2.6 Dashboard to support decision - making

The Climate_CRICES dashboard goes beyond visualizing datasets. It integrates structured metadata about climate change adaptation plans with relevant datasets, enabling users to:

- ✓ **Explore connections** between data and policy
- ✓ **Identify high-priority gaps**
- ✓ **Support decision-making** based on shared frameworks

This is especially relevant given the project's emphasis on cross-border climate adaptation, where aligned strategies and interoperable data are often lacking. The structured methodology developed by the partnership is a major step forward in addressing this gap.

The final version of the dashboard will further support integrated decision-making by providing transparent access to both strategies and the data underpinning them, creating a powerful resource for regional and national adaptation efforts across Central Europe. The dashboard will present both the structured metadata on strategic plans and the datasets themselves, enabling deeper insights into how plans are implemented and monitored.

The application form emphasized the importance of “data at trans-border level, based on common classification criteria”—a foundational concept for the entire project. Consequently, the partnership has worked diligently to establish a common classification system for impacts, risks, indicators, objectives and measures. This shared system makes it possible to compare strategies across different partners and countries.

Regions Comparison

Select a region...

... to compare with

Burgenland	Grad Zagreb	Piemonte	Tolna
Dolnośląskie	Liberecký kraj	Sachsen	Veneto

Burgenland	Grad Zagreb	Piemonte	Tolna
Dolnośląskie	Liberecký kraj	Sachsen	Veneto

Policies Comparison

Select a policy...

... to compare with

- Search
- Climate resilience plan - City of Turin
 - Climate Strategy of Bács-Kiskun County
 - Climate Strategy of Tolna County
 - Drought Effects Counteracting Plan (2021)

- Search
- Action plan for adaptation to climate change in the Liberec region (2021)**
 - Action Plan for Climate Neutrality in the Lower Silesian Voivodeship (...)
 - Austrian Strategy for adaptation to climate Change (2024)

SRACC (Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy)

Action plan for adaptation to climate change in the Liberec region (2021)

Veneto Region
Coverage Area

Liberecky Region
Coverage Area

ITALY
Country

CZECH REPUBLIC
Country

37
Objectives

48
Measures

N/A
Actions

33
Objectives

29
Measures

50
Actions

Objectives

Objectives

Figure 10 - First version of the Climate_CRICES Dashboard Prototype, example of Policies comparison for Piemonte and Veneto Regions, Italy

In the process, the team identified overlaps among indicators and impacts, enabling the creation of a consolidated list that is now shared across the partnership.

Importantly, this structured and harmonized approach has resulted in a dashboard that is not only technically robust but also accessible and useful to policymakers. The dashboard helps them visualise their own strategies and compare them with others: identifying missing objectives, seeing which actions are prioritized by other partners, and exploring additional data that could enhance their own work.

The figure below provides an overview of the navigation structure for the current prototype of the **Climate_CRICES dashboard**. It illustrates how users can interact with different modules and access various types of content, with a focus on clarity and usability.

Figure 11 - Dashboard Introduction: Navigation Map of the Current Prototype

3 Outcomes of Partner's analyses

3.1 List of missing indicators (from strategies and plans)

The indicators, whose identification was described above, in the beginning of the Deliverable, underwent a further phase of impact assessment, where it was determined whether they are relevant in the context of the individual areas of strategic documents - the area of relevance (Relevancy). Based on a detailed review of selected strategic documents within the project consortium, it was examined whether the indicator is considered in the document (Policy) and whether data for its evaluation are available (Data). This three information were recorded for each identified indicator in 7.2 Table summarizing the indicators.

A number of indicators are considered highly relevant across nearly all partners (e.g., *Hot days*, *Total annual precipitation*, *Number of heavy rainfall days*,..). However, policy coverage and data availability for some of these indicators lag behind their perceived relevance. *Hot days* and *Heavy precipitation* indicators are strong examples where relevance, policy, and data availability are relatively aligned - indicating these are well-recognized and actionable areas. There are several indicators where these three areas are not aligned.

Examples of indicators with high relevance but low policy inclusion:

- *Duration of soil moisture droughts*: Relevant for all (12), but mentioned only in 3 policy documents
- *Daily max flow*: Relevant for all (12), mentioned in only 5 policies

→ *This suggests a need for better integration of key climate stress indicators into strategic documents*

Examples of indicators with poor data availability despite high relevance:

- *Common bird index*: Relevant for 11, but data are not available in any of the cases
- *Potential hail index (PHI)*: Relevant for 11, but data are not available in any of the cases

→ *Some indicators may require improved monitoring infrastructure or access to existing datasets*

Examples of indicators with high relevance but low both policy inclusion and data availability:

- *Climatic Impact Indicator (CII)*: Relevant for 11 case study areas, but mentioned in 2 policy documents with 0 data availability
- *Vegetation productivity*: Relevant for 11 out of the total 12 areas, mentioned in 3 policy documents with 0 data availability

→ *The need for both improved data collection and stronger policy recognition of key indicators. Integrating such indicators into monitoring systems and strategic planning could enhance the*

understanding of long-term climate impacts and ecosystem health.

3.2 List of additional important indicators (from strategies and plans)

There are several important impacts and indicators that are currently missing in the common lists. The existing set of indicators does not fully reflect the breadth of national and regional strategies, which often address a wider range of issues beyond heat and drought, flooding, and biodiversity. These strategies also consider other critical areas such as public health, social vulnerability, and economic resilience.

Several missing indicators have been identified in three areas of project focus. Several concrete examples are provided below for each thematic area.

1) Heat and Drought

- Regional variability in agricultural impacts, particularly in already dry areas
- Sector-specific stress, such as urban infrastructure (e.g., road deformation) due to extreme heat
- Indirect effects, like increased reliance on cooling systems, leading to higher energy demands

2) Flooding

- Higher flood risks during winter months due to shifting precipitation patterns
- Increased intensity and frequency of heavy rainfall, causing pluvial and fluvial flooding risks or soil erosion and sediment transport into water bodies

3) Impact on Biodiversity

- Habitat degradation driven by extreme weather events (e.g., wildfires, droughts)
- Loss of biodiversity due to shifts in species distribution and loss of habitats, or spread of invasive species (Neobiota) and increased risks from new pests and pathogens
- Changes in aquatic ecosystems due to higher water temperatures and altered hydrological cycles

3.3 Inputs from the First Local Workshops (Missing and additional indicators)

The first round of local stakeholder workshops held across partner regions provided valuable insights into both the practical implementation of climate adaptation strategies and the gaps in data and indicators currently used to inform them. These workshops helped validate the common set of indicators proposed by the project and revealed additional needs and local priorities not fully captured by the existing framework.

Stakeholders emphasized the importance of including indicators that reflect region-specific challenges and sectoral vulnerabilities—particularly in agriculture, water management, urban infrastructure, and biodiversity conservation. In many cases, participants also highlighted

limitations in data availability, uneven update cycles, or the lack of integration of locally relevant indicators into formal strategies.

Thematic Area 1: Heat and Drought

Several regions highlighted:

- Agricultural vulnerability, especially in already dry or semi-arid areas
- Urban infrastructure stress, such as road surface deformation due to prolonged heatwaves
- Indirect impacts like rising energy demand from increased use of cooling systems

Proposed additional indicators:

- Energy use for cooling
- Soil moisture anomalies at urban and regional scales
- Thermal stress indices for sensitive population groups

Thematic Area 2: Flooding

Identified monitoring needs:

- Seasonal shifts in flood risk, particularly increased winter precipitation
- Pluvial and fluvial flood frequency, especially related to extreme rainfall events
- Soil erosion and sediment transport, with direct consequences for water quality and ecosystem health

Suggested indicators:

- Intensity and frequency of short-duration heavy rainfall events
- Sediment load measurements in rivers and streams
- Winter precipitation index

Thematic Area 3: Biodiversity

Key concerns:

- Habitat degradation due to fires, droughts, and heatwaves
- Loss of species driven by climate-induced shifts or invasive species
- Ecosystem health, particularly in aquatic systems

Suggested indicators:

- Indicators on habitat quality and connectivity
- Metrics on invasive species prevalence (e.g., neobiota tracking)
- Aquatic ecosystem temperature profiles and species composition changes

Regional Examples:

- **CDDA**: Emphasis on viticulture adaptation, Winkler and Huglin indices, and pest/disease tracking
- **Liberec Region**: Needs for updated biodiversity indicators, erosion, and groundwater monitoring
- **Poland**: Strong interest in biodiversity data and dashboard usability
- **Veneto/ARPAV**: Issues with fragmented data, interest in harmonization, and dashboard sustainability

4 Data-gaps and Solutions

4.1 Based on the dataset analysis

By May 2025, the partnership identified and provided **223 Regional data sources** for the Climate_CRICES dashboard. This followed an in-depth analysis of indicator requirements, data availability across participating countries, and relevance to the project’s objectives. Each data source was carefully reviewed, with a particular focus on accuracy, consistency, and alignment with open-data principles. All sources were verified as primary and confirmed to be open access, ensuring transparency and usability across the platform.

The graph and table below presents the number of datasets contributed by each partner for their respective pilot area:

Figure 12 - Regional Dataset Contributions by Partner as of May 2025

Table 1 - Climate_CRICES number of datasets contributed by each partner for their respective pilot area

Partner ID	Partner name	N. of Datasets
PP02	Veneto Region, ARPA, Italy	9
PP03	CSI, Italy	13
PP04	Forschung Burgenland	20
PP05	Central Danube Development Agency Nonprofit Ltd.	0
PP06	North-West Croatia Regional Energy and Climate Agency	58
PP07	Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development	79
PP08	Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences	2
PP09	University of Usti, Institute for Economic and Environmental Policy	42
Total		223

To address data gaps in the project’s pilot areas—and to ensure scalability of the Climate_CRICES analysis across Central Europe—the partnership explored the potential use of European and global datasets.

The use of European and global data sources to feed the calculation of the indicators selected in the partners' common list can offer the following advantages:

- availability of data for all the project partner regions
- uniformity of data and methodology
- guarantee of data updating
- availability of a large time series
- availability of many updated predictive models
- single data source, with standard formats

However, the use of these data sources can also lead to disadvantages, regarding the resolution of data which could be less detailed than data provided by national and regional agencies.

Figure 13- Assessment of European and Global Data Sources: Relevance, Strengths, and Limitations for Climate_CRICES

The analysis of possible European and global data sources started from the analysis of data availability among the various partners. Not all partners can guarantee the availability of data relating to the main climatic and environmental variables (e.g. heating and cooling degree days, total precipitation, duration and intensity of drought, maximum flow, land cover and others). The most uncovered sector is animal and plant biodiversity, with many indicators that are completely uncovered or available from few partners, including relevant indicators such as the conservation status of species under the EU Habitats Directive.

The analysis of European and global sources has led to the production of a shared draft with the list of possible data sources:

- Copernicus and Cordex for data on temperatures and precipitation, flow and ecological status of rivers, air and soil humidity (JRC data also available), change in land cover (CORINE land cover), vegetation productivity, ecosystems, snow, forest fires (data also available from EEA and NASA)
- Eurostat for data on the common bird index, the grassland butterfly index
- NASA for data on hail risk (PANGAEA data also available)
- EEA for data on forests and landscape fragmentation
- EM-DAT for data on number of victims and damage to infrastructure

The partnership selected in total 64 European/global data sources by May 2025.

Figure 14 - Number of Global /European datasets by Source

Table 2: Number of datasets per source

Global Data source	N. of Datasets
Copernicus	31
Eurocordex	13
Persiann	1
NASA	3
European Drought Observatory	2
Eurostat	2
WISE Freshwater	1
EEA	4
European Severe Storms Laboratory	1
PANGAEA	1
Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	1
EFAS	1
Public EM-DAT	2
European Severe Weather Database	1
Total	64

Source

- NASA
- Copernicus
- Eumetstat
- other

Content

- Meteorological data
- Climate data
- Satellite data on soil, forests and hydrograph

Impact Indicator ID	Indicator name	data source	comments	spatial coverage	spatial resolution	temporal coverage	temporal resolution	(R)eady, (S)imilar, (C)alculate	access	licence
11	Hot days	copernicus, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	to 2100	daily	C		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
12	Heatwave days	copernicus, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	1951 - 2100	daily	C		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
13	Tropical nights	eurocordex, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.25deg	1940-2100	daily	R		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
14	Maximum consecutive five-day precipitation	eurocordex, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	1951 - 2100	daily	C		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
15	Mean temperature	copernicus, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.25deg	1940-2100	year	R		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
16	Maximum Daily Air Temperature	eurocordex, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	1951 - 2100	3h+	R		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
17	Growing degree days	copernicus, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe (gridded, regional layer: NUTS-Level 1+2; region RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5)	0.25deg	1940-2100	monthly, seasonal, yearly	R	registration required	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
18	Heating degree days	eurocordex, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	1951 - 2100	day	C		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus
19	Cooling degree days	eurocordex, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus , https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus	historical-projections	Europe	0.11deg	1951 - 2100	day	C		https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus

Figure 15 - Climate_CRICES Data and metadata from Global data sources, each data source was assigned to impacts

A recurring challenge in cross-border climate adaptation planning is the diversity of data sources—each developed under different conditions, with varying resolutions, assumptions, and modeling approaches. This heterogeneity affects everything from indicator comparability to the coherence of adaptation strategies across regions.

In Climate_CRICES, this issue is especially relevant as partners aim to bring together regional, national, and global datasets within a unified dashboard environment. However, **full integration of these datasets—into a seamless, interoperable system—is beyond the scope of the project**, and indeed beyond the capacity of most international initiatives without centralized governance or data standards.

Instead, Climate_CRICES addresses this challenge through **transparency and structured comparability**. By linking each indicator to detailed metadata—including data origin, methodology, and geographic/temporal resolution—the dashboard helps users understand the context and limitations of the information they are viewing. Where gaps or inconsistencies exist, they are not hidden but made visible.

Rather than forcing artificial alignment of incompatible datasets, the project aims to **support informed dialogue and contextual interpretation**, allowing decision-makers to work with the best available information while understanding its limitations.

In short, Climate_CRICES is not an integrated data platform in the technical sense. It is a **facilitating tool**—one that improves visibility, supports structured comparison, and builds a shared understanding of climate adaptation challenges across Central Europe.

7.3 Workflow Timeline for Data Structuring and Integration presents the process timeline, showing the key stages of work carried out so far, the current status, and the planned steps for completing the next phases of the data improvement for the Dashboard.

4.2 Based on the cross-border cooperation analysis

The cross-border region shared by the Czech Republic, Germany, and Poland faces common climate-related challenges, such as extreme weather events, droughts, and ecosystem degradation. However, effective cooperation in climate change adaptation is hindered by several systemic issues:

1. Fragmentation of Adaptation Strategies

Climate adaptation efforts are primarily addressed at the national level, resulting in fragmented approaches at cross-border level:

- There is no overarching cross-border adaptation strategy that unifies the efforts of all three countries.
- National adaptation documents are developed independently, with differing priorities, instruments, and timelines.
- The absence of a shared vision and integrated approach limits the effectiveness of responses to transboundary climate impacts.

2. Formal Coordination Without Substantial Integration

While national strategies are sometimes summarized in joint cross-border documents, these efforts are often formal and descriptive rather than truly strategic:

- Cross-border summaries typically list individual national measures without aligning them or setting common goals.
- There is a lack of joint planning, implementation, and evaluation frameworks.

3. Lack of Coordinated Action

Key obstacles to effective cooperation include:

- The absence of permanent coordination platforms or institutions responsible for the comprehensive management of cross-border adaptation efforts. (This is partly addressed by the Euroregion Neisse - Nisa - Nysa and at river basin level by the International Commission for the Protection of the Odra River, though these do not comprehensively cover all climate change impacts).
- Differing legal and institutional frameworks, making joint project implementation complex.
- Limited practical cooperation at the level of local governments, land managers, and other key stakeholders.

4. Fragmented Data Sharing and Information Exchange

Efficient climate adaptation requires access to shared and comparable data, however:

- Data collection methodologies differ across countries, complicating integration and joint analysis.
- A common cross-border database for environmental and climate data is lacking.
- The exchange of best practices, scientific findings, and project outcomes is limited, often tied to specific projects without continuous follow-up.

5 Lessons Learned

Implementing Deliverable D.1.3.2 provided valuable insights into the practical and strategic challenges of assembling, structuring and making climate-related data usable across different levels of governance and regions in Central Europe. Several key lessons emerged from the process:

Standardisation enables comparability

The diversity of climate adaptation plans and indicators across countries and regions makes comparison difficult without a common framework. Developing a shared methodology based on structured metadata and defined entities (impacts, risks, indicators, objectives and measures) proved essential for enabling cross-border analysis and visualisation.

Metadata Matters More Than Raw Data

Many existing datasets are technically robust, yet disconnected from the policy context. Including metadata such as territorial scope, update frequency, source transparency and policy relevance significantly improves data usability for strategic decision-making.

Integration requires transparency, not uniformity

True interoperability remains a major challenge, particularly when working with datasets that vary in resolution, scope and modelling assumptions. Climate_CRICES recognises that it is not possible to resolve these differences within a single platform, but making them visible through transparent metadata and relationship mapping is already a valuable outcome.

Regional engagement is crucial

Workshops and feedback from partners were instrumental in identifying relevant indicators, understanding context-specific data gaps, and aligning dashboard functionalities with actual user needs. This iterative, participatory process ensures that the outputs are grounded in real regional priorities rather than theoretical assumptions.

Gaps are opportunities

Where data was missing or inaccessible, partners used this as a basis for identifying strategic priorities and initiating discussions with local and national institutions. Rather than being a limitation, the visibility of gaps has become a driver for capacity-building and future cooperation.

Global Data Sources Are Useful—but Require Careful Interpretation

European and global datasets—such as those from Copernicus, EURO-CORDEX, or the World Bank—provide valuable baseline information, particularly where regional data is missing. However, their resolution, assumptions, and sectoral relevance often differ from local needs. Climate_CRICES

learned that these sources must be used carefully and always accompanied by clear metadata to avoid misinterpretation. When transparently documented and contextually integrated, they can complement regional efforts and enable wider benchmarking.

These lessons have not only shaped the structure of the Climate_CRICES dashboard, but also the partnership's approach to data governance, collaboration and the link between climate science and public policy. The partnership offers a transferable model for similar cross-border or multi-level adaptation initiatives.

6 Conclusions

The Climate_CRICES project has made significant progress in identifying, structuring, and harmonizing climate-related data and indicators across Central Europe. Through a coordinated effort by all partners, this deliverable maps the existing data landscape, highlights persistent gaps, and proposes practical, scalable solutions that are both technically sound and policy-relevant.

While many existing climate platforms offer detailed data, they often lack accessibility and connection to strategic adaptation planning. Climate_CRICES does not attempt to centralize or replace these systems, but rather to **facilitate structured comparison**, increase **transparency**, and enable **evidence-based decision-making** through a common classification and metadata framework.

The project successfully:

- Developed a shared methodology to extract and relate data from climate adaptation plans
- Identified 223 regional and 64 global data sources, assessed for openness and relevance
- Created a policy-aware dashboard structure that makes climate adaptation plans comparable across borders.

By focusing on metadata quality, relationship mapping, and user-friendly visualization, Climate_CRICES offers a way forward even in the face of fragmented data systems.

In this way, the project will deliver more than a dashboard—it will build a foundation for long-term, cross-border cooperation on climate adaptation, enabling mutual learning, strategic benchmarking, and informed regional planning.

7 Annexes

Climate_CRICES

7.1 Table summarizing the impacts (climate change risks)

Impact	Partners	PP02	PP03	PP04	PP05 TVM	PP05 KDMFT	PP05 BKVM	PP06	PP07	PP08 PO08	PP08 PO14	PP08 PO15	PP09 LR	Total
Risk to population from increased heat	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
Impacts of climate change on heating and cooling energy demand	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	10
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	11
Risk of loss of biodiversity	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Measures	y		y	n	n	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	8
Increased risk of wildfire	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	10
	Measures	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	8
Risk to marine coastal ecosystem services due to loss of habitat-forming species	Relevancy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	1
	Policy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n					n	1
	Measures	y	n	n	n	n	n	n					n	1
Population at risk from exposure to urban droughts	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	11
	Measures	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	10
Health risks from water pollution exposure and sanitation in cities	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Measures	y	n	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	9
	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12

Risk of losses in crop production due to dry conditions	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	Climate CRICES y	y	y	y	y	12
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
Risk of losses in crop production due to extreme precipitation	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	10
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	10
Risk of losses in crop production due to extreme temperatures	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	(y)	n	y	y	10
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	11
Risk of water scarcity to multiple interconnected sectors	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	10
	Measures	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Risk to coastal communities from flooding and sea level rise due to loss of coastal habitat	Relevancy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	1
	Policy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n				n	1
	Measures	y	n	n	n	n	n	n				n	1
Risks of mortality and damage to (coastal) infrastructure and economic assets due to coastal flooding (Low-lying European coastal zones (...))	Relevancy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	1
	Policy	y	n	n	n	n	n	n				n	1
	Measures	y	n	n	n	n	n	n				n	1
Risks of mortality and damage to infrastructure and economic assets due river flooding	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Measures	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Risks of mortality and damage to infrastructure and economic assets due inland flooding	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12

Reduction in habitat availability of cold-adapted groups	Relevancy	y		y	n	n	n	Climate CRICES Y	y	n	y	7
	Policy	y		y	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	4
	Measures	y		y	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	5
Changes in phenology	Relevancy	y		y	n	n	n	y	y	y	y	7
	Policy	y		y	n	n	n	y	n	y	y	6
	Measures	y		y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	4
Increased soil erosion due to extreme precipitation	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	11
	Measures	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	10
Physical changes in freshwater systems	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	10
	Policy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	9
	Measures	y		n	n	y	y	y	y	y	n	7
Increased risk of hails	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	(y)	y	y	10
	Policy	y		y	y	n	y	y	y	n	n	8
	Measures	y		y	n	n	y	y	y	n	n	5
Change in climatic suitability for broadleaf and needleleaf trees	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		y	n	y	y	n	y	n	n	6
	Measures	y		y	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	5
Trends (Changes) in spring phenology (species-specific trends of spring leaf unfolding)	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	10
	Policy	y		y	y	n	y	n	n	(y)	n	5
	Measures	y		y	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	4
Loss of snow cover and its duration	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	11
	Policy	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	y	n	8
	Measures	y	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	4
Land Cover and Land-use change	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	n	y	9
	Measures	y	y	y	n	y	n	n	y	n	y	8

7.2 Table summarizing the indicators

Climate_CRICES

	Partners	PP02	PP03	PP04	PP05 Tolna	PP05 CDPA	PP05 BK	PP06	PP07	PP08 PO08	PPO PO14	PP09 HN	PP09 LR	Total
Hot days	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	9
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
Heatwave days	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	y	n	y	y	n	n	n	y	y	7
	Data	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Tropical nights	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	8
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	11
Maximum consecutive five-day precipitation	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	?	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
Mean temperature	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	y	n	y	y	(y)	y	n	y	y	8
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
Maximum Daily Air Temperature	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	8
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y		y	y	y	y	11
Growing degree days	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11

	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	Climate_ORICES			n	n	y	4
	Data	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Heating degree days	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	y	4
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	y	y	y	y	10
Cooling degree days	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y	y	y	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	5
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	11
Frost days	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	10
	Policy	y		n	y	n	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	7
	Data	y		y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	10
Total annual precipitation	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	?	n	y	n	y	y	(n)	y	n	y	y	7
	Data	y	?	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Consecutive dry days	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	n	n	y	6
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	11
Duration of meteorological droughts	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	y	4
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		y	y	y	y	10
Magnitude of meteorological droughts	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	3

	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	Climate_ORICES	y	y	y	y	10
Duration of soil moisture droughts	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	3
	Data	n	y	n	n	n	n	n		n	n	y	3
Days with fire danger exceeding a threshold	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	y	4
	Data	y		n	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	y	5
Standard Precipitation Index (SPI)	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	5
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		y	y	y	10
Daily max flow	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	3
	Data	y	y	n	y	y	y	n		n	n	y	7
Number of days with precipitation (rain) greater than or equal to 30 mm/d	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	y	n	n	5
	Data	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
Climatic water balance	Relevancy	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y	n	n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	4
	Data	y	n	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	n	9
Standardized Snowmelt and Rain Index (SMRI)	Relevancy	n	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	10
	Policy	n	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n/y	n	1

Change in land cover	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	n	y	Climate, CRICES	y	y	y	11		
	Policy	y	y	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	y (as a monitoring indicator)	y	5
	Data	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	10
climatic impact indicator (CII)	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	?	0
Community temperature index (CTI)	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	(n)	n	n	n	n	0
Vegetation productivity	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	y	3
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0
change in the distribution of demersal fish in response to observed rise in sea surface temperatures	Relevancy	y		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	1
	Policy	y		n	n	n	n	n			n	n	n	1
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n			n	n	n	0
Common bird index	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n		(y)	n	n	0
Grassland butterfly index	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	0

Changes in fish distribution in Europe's seas (Temporal development of the ratio of the number of Lusitanian species to the number of Boreal species)	Relevancy	y		n	n	y	n	Climate_ORICES		n	n	n	2
	Policy	y		n	n	n	n	n		n	n	n	1
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n		n	n	n	0
Ecosystem coverage in Europe	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	y	4
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	2
Ecological status of surface waters in Europe	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	y	n	n	4
	Data	y		n	y	y	y	n		n	n	y	5
Conservation status of species under the EU Habitats Directive	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n			(y)	n	0
Abundance and distribution of selected species in Europe	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n		n	n	n	0
Drought impact area	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	y	n	y	y	n	n	n	n	5
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	2
Forest fires in Europe	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	y	n	y	y	y	n	n	n	6
	Data	y		n	n	n	n	n		n	n	n	2

Potential hail index (PHI)	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	Climate_VRICES	y	y	y	11	
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	2	
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	?	0	
Climatically suitable areas for bumblebees	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	1
Spring snow cover - march snow mass in Europe (excluding mountain areas) - change in Northern hemisphere spring snow cover extent	Relevancy	n		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	10
	Policy	n		n	n	n	y	n	n	y	n	y	3
	Data	n		y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	2
Forest connectivity indicator	Relevancy	y		y	y	n	y	y	y	y	n	y	9
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	y	3
	Data	n		n	y	y	y	n	n	n	n	n	3
Share of woody landscape features on agricultural area in the EU	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	10
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	2
	Data	n		n	y	y	y	n	n	n	n	y	4
Landscape fragmentation pressure in Europe	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	y	3
	Data	n		n				n		n	n	?	0
Soil moisture deficit	Relevancy	y		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	11
	Policy	y		n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n	y	4
	Data	n		n	n	n	n	n		n	n	y	2

Losses in crops and agricultural production	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	Climate_VRICES	y	y	y	11		
	Policy	y	y	n	y	n	Y	n	n	n	n	y	5	
	Data	n	n	n	y	y	y	y		n	n	?	?	4
Number of flood victims	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	Y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	y (as monitoring indicator)	y	4
	Data	n	n	n	y	y	y	y		y	y	y	y	8
Losses in infrastructure	Relevancy	y	y	y	y	y	y	Y	y	y	y	y	y	12
	Policy	y	y	n	y	n	y	Y	y	n	n	y (as monitoring indicator)	y	7
	Data	n	n	n	y	y	y	Y		y	n	y	y	7

7.3 Workflow Timeline for Data Structuring and Integration

Climate_CRICES

	2 Project Period						3 Project Period						4 Project Period					5 Project Period							
	Dez 24	Jan 25	Feb 25	Mrz 25	Apr 25	Mai 25	Jun 25	Jul 25	Aug 25	Sep 25	Okt 25	Nov 25	Dez 25	Jan 26	Feb 26	Mrz 26	Apr 26	Mai 26	Jun 26	Jul 26	Aug 26	Sep 26	Okt 26	Nov 26	
Collection of metadata related to indicators					Development and Release of the First Dashboard Prototype																				
Identification of regional datasets for indicator or context evaluation																									
Definition of relationships between regional datasets and indicators																									
Identification of global datasets for indicator evaluation																									
Refinement of the list of relevant indicators in relation to policies																									
Clarify whether Working Groups need to deliver indicators																									
For selected indicators, define a single global dataset for evaluation																									
Possible identification of regional datasets to cover indicators not supported by international datasets																									

Identification of indicators not covered by any available dataset
Possible identification of alternative regional datasets for evaluating indicators already covered by international datasets
Preparation of international datasets for use in the dashboard
Possible preparation of regional datasets for use in the dashboard

			Climate_CRICES									